

IMPROVING THE ORGANIZATION OF LANDSCAPING SERVICES – TIME REQUIREMENTS

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Abstract. *This article is devoted to landscape services, which have become one of the most global problems in the world. It is emphasized that the lack of attention to the improvement of this network today is one of the most pressing problems of this type of services. At the same time, the most important aspects of landscaping are illustrated with examples, proposals and recommendations for the development of this type of services are developed.*

Keywords: *landscaping, landscaping services, urban improvement, landscaping, cities, district centers, modern appearance, landscaping facilities, landscaping.*

Introduction

Landscaping services, which is one of the most global problems in the world today, cover all developed and developing countries. Especially in the capitals of countries around the world, environmental cleanliness is in the focus of attention of all levels of government, political parties, social movements, the media, as well as the population.

Literature review

In order to effectively develop landscaping services and pay special attention to this type of service, President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev's Resolution No. PQ-4351 "On Additional Measures to Improve the Efficiency of Work in the Field of Improvement of Settlements" adopted on June 4, according to which In order to address this issue, it is necessary to take consistent measures to improve landscaping through the establishment of landscaping departments on the basis of existing organizations (divisions) on landscaping in the districts and cities of the country. new tasks for the development and updating of the database, standards, urban planning norms and regulations have been identified.

Research methodology

In the implementation of the study, conclusions and recommendations were formed as a result of the analysis of indicators of effective development of landscaping services through economic methods. In addition, the methods of analysis and synthesis were effectively used in the study of landscaping by zoning in the conduct of scientific research.

Analysis and results

Analyzing the day-to-day operations of cities around the world is a challenge to addressing a number of issues in that city. Most importantly, the development of landscaping services is another important indicator that serves to enhance the status of cities, while ensuring economic and social stability. However, one of the most important problems in the development of landscaping services is the lack of focus on improving this sector today.

Landscaping services, so to speak, are the servants within the enclosure. It's a process that changes the mood of each of us throughout the day, either in a very beautiful way or vice versa. It is advisable to study this type of service into the following objects.

Areas of landscaping - landscaping, in front of regional, district, multi-storey buildings, neighborhoods and other areas, including playgrounds, courtyards, functional planning structures, administrative buildings of districts and urban districts, as well as in accordance with the principles of a single town-planning regulation isolated areas (security zones) or visual-spatial perception (area with buildings, adjacent territory and street with buildings), other specially defined areas.

Landscaping standards - a normalized set of elements of landscaping of specially designated areas, where the norms and rules of landscaping are determined, controlled by the norms and rules of their placement in this area.

Examples of such areas are:

- technical (safety and operation) of various functional purposes, pedestrian communications, roads, public places, public places and zones, housing development, sanitary and protective zones of industrial development, recreation areas, residential street and road network, engineering communications zones.

Cleaning of areas - this requires the timely completion of tasks related to the collection of industrial and consumer waste, other garbage, snow, transportation to designated areas, as well as other measures aimed at ensuring the ecological and sanitary-epidemiological well-being of the population and environmental protection. In the conditions of our country, the size of courtyard plots is 300-600 m², depending on the characteristics of the urban situation.

The estimated density of the housing stock in the territory of residential districts and neighborhoods shall be taken in accordance with Tables 1 and 2.

It is not allowed to increase the existing density of residential buildings in the zones of environmental disasters and emergencies identified in accordance with the criteria for assessing the environmental condition of the territories without taking the necessary measures for environmental protection.

Table 1.

Density of housing stock for the total area 1 ha, m²

Floor of residential houses	Residential houses with plots of land		Multi-family apartment buildings								
	1-2 yards	2 blocks	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	12
Density of housing stock, at least	1200	1800	2200	3900	4200	4800	5100	5400	5700	6300	6700

Notes: 1. The density of the housing stock may be changed with appropriate justification during construction and reconstruction in the territory of urban settlements.

In the construction of multi-storey buildings, the density of the housing stock should be taken according to the medium harmonic formula:

$$\frac{100}{\frac{a_1}{n_1} + \frac{a_2}{n_2} + \frac{a_3}{n_3} + \dots}$$

by erda a_1, a_2, a_3 - the total area of multi-storey residential buildings accepted in the project, as a percentage of the total area of all residential buildings in the area;

n_1, n_2, n_3 - density of the housing stock, determined from Table 2, m^2 / ha , depending on the number of storeys of the adopted buildings.

In determining the density of the housing stock in settlements with a population less than the specified number for one area, service institutions and enterprises, as well as land plots occupied with greenery for the settlement as a whole are not taken into account.

Table 2.

Density of the housing stock with a total area of 1 for the territory of the residential district, m^2

Floor of residential houses	Residential houses with plots of land										
	1-2 yards	2 blocks	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	12
Density of housing stock, at least	700	1200	2200	2600	2800	3100	3200	3400	3500	3700	3900

Notes: 1. When calculating the density of the housing stock, the area of service establishments and enterprises, car maintenance enterprises and other objects of city significance located in the residential area shall be excluded from the area of the residential area.

In cases where the residential district is bordered by main streets, the area of the residential district shall include half the width of the main streets bordering it.

The volume of demolition of the base structure in the reconstruction of districts with a predominance of pre-existing capital housing will be determined based on the urban development conditions of the region. Construction of attic floors in the zones of historical installations is allowed in accordance with the general stylistic unity of the historical environment, preservation of historically formed landscape views of historical and cultural monuments. [3]

Landscaping areas can be divided into 3 main parts:

Figure 1.

Internal areas - fronts of provinces, districts, high-rise buildings, neighborhoods and other areas, including playgrounds, courtyards, functional planning structures, administrative buildings of districts and urban districts, as well as areas (security zones) or visual -spatial perception (area with buildings, adjacent territory and street with buildings), includes other specially defined areas.

When landscaping the interior, first of all, these areas are beautified with the help of various flower beds, species of flower varieties that look beautiful in hanging pots (fucus, surfinia, pelargonium).

When landscaping outdoor areas, it is advisable to decorate the perimeter of the building or structure with various types of outdoor trees, shrubs, spruces and roses.

Special attention is paid to irrigation and drainage systems in the landscaping of the intermediate part. An important part of this area is usually occupied by lawns, which makes it extremely convenient for people to relax.

The formation of a modern image of existing cities and settlements in the country, the harmonization of road transport and engineering-communication infrastructure with modern urban planning norms and requirements will play an important role in the future economy and development of the country.

Conclusion

As a result, we can say that the existing cities and districts of the country will be beautified, the maintenance and operation of facilities will be carried out in a timely and quality manner.

The issues of landscaping of streets, squares, alleys, monuments and other public green areas of the country, agro-technical measures for the care of trees, the fight against their pests and diseases are gradually being addressed.

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